

**DEVELOPMENT OF FREEZE-DRIED
HA/SA MICRONEEDLE PATCHES FOR
TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY OF
INSULIN**

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CERTIFICATE

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DEDICATION

With deep reverence and gratitude,

We dedicate this work to our families, whose constant encouragement made this journey possible, and to our mentors and teachers, whose guidance shaped every step of this project.

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First and foremost, all praise and thanks to God for granting us the strength, patience, and perseverance to successfully complete our Final Year Design Project. We would like to express our sincere gratitude to our supervisor, Dr. Usman Liaqat, for his continuous guidance, valuable insights, and dedicated support throughout the course of this research. His technical expertise and mentorship have been pivotal in helping us overcome challenges and stay focused on our objectives. Special thanks to the faculty and lab staff of the Department of Materials Engineering, SCME, NUST, for facilitating our experimental work by providing access to essential laboratory equipment and analytical tools. Lastly, we are deeply grateful to our families for their unconditional support and prayers. Their constant encouragement gave us the motivation to put our best foot forward at every stage of this project.

ABSTRACT

Transdermal drug delivery is a promising alternative to traditional methods of drug delivery, providing a non-invasive route for administering therapeutic agents while avoiding complications like gastrointestinal degradation and first-pass metabolism. Our project explores the design and fabrication of microneedles to improve drug delivery efficiency and patient comfort in treating diabetes. Five microneedle designs were developed in SolidWorks, each with distinct geometries and aspect ratios, including conical, pyramidal, cylindrical, and hybrid structures. Prototypes were fabricated using SLA 3D printing, with a resolution of up to 20 microns, to ensure high precision in the master molds. Microneedles are being developed using a blend of gelatin-sodium alginate and hyaluronic acid, which offers a biodegradable, biocompatible, and mechanically robust matrix for drug delivery.

The patches were evaluated through mechanical strength testing, optical microscopy, FTIR, XRD, and swelling studies. Compression testing confirmed adequate strength (~2.583 N total), while microscopy and FTIR validated structural and chemical integrity. Swelling tests showed high hydration capacity, supporting efficient drug diffusion. In vitro release studies using lysozyme as a model drug were conducted via UV-Vis spectroscopy at 280 nm. Drug release varied with needle geometry, with conical designs achieving the highest (~82%) cumulative release. Freeze-drying and CaCl₂ crosslinking enhanced both mechanical stability and release performance. These findings highlight the potential of biopolymer microneedles as a safe, effective, and patient-friendly platform for insulin delivery

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INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Microneedles (MNs) offer a promising alternative to traditional subcutaneous insulin injections by addressing the limitations of pain, inconvenience, and potential injection site complications. Recognizing the challenge of delivering insulin through the skin's protective stratum corneum, MNs are designed as microscopic needles that penetrate the epidermis, creating microchannels for drug transport without stimulating pain receptors in the dermis. These minimally invasive devices utilize various mechanisms for insulin delivery, including pore formation, the use of dissolving or swelling biocompatible materials that release encapsulated insulin upon insertion and absorption of interstitial fluid to form a drug-releasing hydrogel [1]. This approach offers several advantages: painless application improves patient compliance, bypassing first-pass metabolism enhances insulin bioavailability, and certain MN designs, particularly those that swell into hydrogels, enable sustained insulin release, potentially mimicking physiological insulin secretion more effectively than bolus injections. This technology holds potential for integration with glucose sensors in closed-loop systems, offering real-time insulin delivery adjustments. In summary, MNs represent a significant advancement in non-invasive insulin delivery, addressing key challenges associated with traditional methods and paving the way for improved diabetes management.

1.2 Limitations of Conventional Drug Delivery Systems

Traditional drug delivery systems, primarily oral and intravenous administration, face significant limitations despite their widespread use. Oral delivery suffers from first-pass metabolism that reduces bioavailability, and gastrointestinal variability leading to inconsistent absorption and drug instability. Intravenous administration is invasive, painful, carries infection risks and thrombosis, requires trained personnel,

and can cause rapid, potentially toxic drug concentrations with limited sustained release. Other routes like subcutaneous, intramuscular, transdermal, and pulmonary also have limitations, including pain, variable absorption, skin barrier restrictions, and dependence on patient technique [1]. Beyond route-specific problems, traditional systems generally lack targeted delivery, leading to off-target effects and reduced efficacy, and offer poor control over drug release, resulting in fluctuating drug levels. These limitations highlight the need for advanced drug delivery systems that improve drug availability, stability, targeting, and release profiles to enhance therapeutic outcomes and patient safety.

Figure 1: The pros and cons of potential routes for insulin delivery

1.2.1 Need for Alternative Insulin Delivery Methods

Diabetes mellitus, particularly Type 1 and advanced Type 2, often requires regular insulin administration to maintain glycemic control. Traditionally, subcutaneous insulin injections remain the gold standard; however, they pose numerous challenges including pain, risk of infection, and poor patient compliance. Daily or multiple daily

injections over a lifetime can lead to psychological resistance, needle phobia, and reduced adherence, ultimately worsening patient outcomes [2].

With the growing diabetic population worldwide, particularly in developing countries like Pakistan, there is a critical need for user-friendly, minimally invasive, and more physiologically mimetic insulin delivery systems. Transdermal drug delivery, especially using microneedles, presents a promising alternative by enabling painless, targeted, and sustained insulin release through the skin's outer layer (stratum corneum) without reaching pain receptors. This approach offers improved comfort, reduced medical waste, and the potential for self-administration without clinical assistance.

1.3 Problem Statement

Traditional subcutaneous injections cause pain, risk of infection, and low patient compliance, especially for individuals requiring multiple daily insulin doses. Achieving accurate, consistent, and sustained insulin release is critical. To overcome this problem one route is the synthesis of microneedle patches for the transdermal drug delivery of insulin. This requires improved microneedle designs with controlled release mechanisms and material integrity. Since transdermal delivery is done through the stratum corneum which is the uppermost layer of skin this ensures microneedle insertion causes minimal discomfort and avoids complications such as skin irritation or infections [3]. The problem with the traditional microneedles patches for insulin delivery has a few problems such as difficulty in achieving consistent and controlled release rates of insulin to mimic natural physiological needs.

1.4 Working Principle

Microneedle patches are an array of tiny needles that create microchannels through the stratum corneum, the outermost layer of the skin, without reaching the pain nerves or blood vessels. These microchannels provide a direct pathway for insulin to bypass the skin barrier, improving its absorption into systemic circulation. These

hydrogel microneedles swell upon insertion and allow insulin diffusion without fully dissolving. The microchannels facilitate the diffusion or direct injection of insulin into the interstitial fluid, allowing it to reach the bloodstream. Controlled release systems can be integrated, where microneedle materials regulate the insulin release rate, mimicking basal or bolus insulin delivery [3].

Figure 2: A depiction of microneedle array penetration depth

1.5 Research Objectives

The primary aim of this research is to develop a novel, freeze-dried microneedle patch for the transdermal delivery of insulin, utilizing a biocompatible and biodegradable polymeric system. The microneedle patch is designed to provide painless administration, improved patient compliance, and controlled release of insulin. To achieve this, the following specific objectives were established:

1. Design and explore different microneedle morphologies, including hybrid designs
2. Develop a freeze-dried microneedle patch using a composite polymer system
3. Evaluate and optimize the drug release profile of insulin from the microneedle patch

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview of Microneedle-Based Drug Delivery

Microneedle (MN) technology represents a significant innovation in transdermal drug delivery. It bridges the gap between conventional hypodermic injections and topical patches by offering minimally invasive, painless administration of therapeutic agents across the stratum corneum, the outermost layer of the skin (ranging from 10-20 μm). Microneedles, typically ranging from 150 to 1000 μm in height, are capable of penetrating the stratum corneum without reaching pain receptors in the deeper dermis, thereby ensuring patient compliance and comfort [3].

Microneedles are fabricated in various geometries and formats such as solid, hollow, dissolving, and hydrogel-forming microneedles. Once inserted into the skin, these microneedles swell or dissolve, releasing their payload in a controlled or sustained manner. Research has shown that microneedle-based systems improve bioavailability, reduce first-pass metabolism, and offer potential for self-administration. This makes them an ideal platform for chronic diseases such as diabetes, where patient adherence to injectable regimens is a major concern.

Figure 3: Schematic of drug release from the five different types of MNs

2.2 Materials Used in Microneedle Fabrication

The choice of material is central to the performance, safety, and functionality of microneedles. Materials must exhibit biocompatibility, sufficient mechanical strength, and, in the case of dissolving microneedles, biodegradability [4][5].

Materials used in this project which will be discussed later as well:

- I. **Gelatin:** A natural biopolymer derived from collagen, known for its biocompatibility, film-forming ability, and moderate mechanical strength. Gelatin offers favorable swelling characteristics that support sustained drug release.
- II. **Sodium Alginate:** A polysaccharide extracted from brown algae, alginate is frequently used for ionic crosslinking with Ca^{2+} , forming hydrogels with adjustable stiffness and porosity.
- III. **Hyaluronic Acid:** A naturally occurring glycosaminoglycan, valued for its hydration-retaining ability, cell compatibility, and enhanced permeability. It is increasingly used in skin-targeted delivery systems [6].

Other Commonly Used Materials

Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) and Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA): Synthetic polymers used for their mechanical integrity and ease of processing, often in rapid-dissolving applications [6].

Carboxymethylcellulose (CMC): Provides good film-forming and water-absorbent properties; often used in combination with other biopolymers.

Chitosan: A positively charged, biodegradable polysaccharide with mucoadhesive properties and potential for insulin encapsulation [6].

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) and Poly(glycolic acid) (PGA): Used in solid or coated microneedles, offering slow degradation rates and tunable mechanical strength.

2.3 Fabrication Techniques

Various fabrication techniques have evolved to manufacture microneedle arrays with precision and scalability:

1. **Molding (Micro-molding or Casting):** One of the most widely used methods for polymer microneedles, which we have also used in this project. A master mold is created via photolithography, laser ablation, or 3D printing and is then used to form negative molds (e.g., PDMS) into which biopolymer solutions are poured and dried [7].
2. **3D Printing:** Enables rapid prototyping and design flexibility. Techniques like stereolithography (SLA) or two-photon polymerization allow for highly customized microneedle arrays with intricate geometries [7].

Figure 4: Schematic of microneedles prepared using 3d printing

3. **Laser Cutting and Etching:** Commonly used for metal or silicon microneedles, though more expensive and less suited to biodegradable systems.

Figure 5: Schematic of microneedles prepared through laser etching

4. **Centrifugal Lithography and Drawing Lithography:** Advanced methods that can precisely control microneedle height and shape during fabrication [7].

Figure 6: Schematic showing microneedles fabricated through drawing lithography

2.4 Challenges and Recent Developments in Microneedles

Challenges

The major challenges are mechanical failure. Biopolymer microneedles must be strong enough to penetrate the skin but flexible enough to avoid brittleness. High aspect ratios can reduce structural integrity. Incomplete insertion is another issue, improper application may result in incomplete insertion, affecting drug delivery efficiency. Additionally, biomolecules like insulin are sensitive to temperature and pH, requiring gentle processing and preservation techniques [7].

Recent Developments

Smart microneedles incorporating glucose-responsive or pH-sensitive materials for controlled insulin delivery are being researched currently. Coated wearable microneedle systems are being introduced which are integrated with sensors for feedback-controlled drug delivery. Microneedle patches are also being worked on to be used for delivering vaccines. Furthermore, hydrogel-based microneedles which are the focus of this project are being studied to optimize swelling and mechanical strength to increase drug release rate [8].

These innovations are pushing microneedles toward clinical and commercial readiness, particularly in areas requiring frequent or self-administered dosing.

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT

3.1 Project Plan Overview

Our project is focused on optimizing transdermal drug delivery using microneedles by adjusting their composition and morphology. The idea is to overcome the drawbacks of conventional microneedle systems, such as limited mechanical strength, slow drug release, and discomfort during application. By employing different needle shapes and materials, the goal is to develop a microneedle patch that ensures efficient, painless drug delivery with improved biocompatibility [9].

3.2 Needle Design and 3D Printing

3.2.1 Software Used for Design

All microneedle designs were made using SolidWorks, which provided the precision needed for designing the intricate needle structures. The software allowed for easy modification of key design parameters, such as length, base diameter, and overall geometry. SolidWorks also made it possible to create detailed 3D models that could be directly used for 3D printing, helping in visualizing how the different shape would behave in real life [7].

3.2.2 Design Parameters and Optimization

Five different microneedle designs were developed, each focusing on a different aspect of performance: skin penetration, drug release efficiency, mechanical stability, and patient comfort. Below are the expected effects of each design based on the morphological characteristics of the needles.

Design 1: Medium Aspect-Ratio Pyramidal Needles

- **Length:** 750 μm
- **Base Diameter:** 300 μm

- **Aspect Ratio:** 2.5
- **Needle-to-Needle Spacing:** 800 μm
- **Number of Needles:** 100 (10x10 array)
- **Geometry:** Square Pyramid

Design 1 is our control. The design parameters were obtained from literature [10]. It features pyramidal needles with an aspect ratio of 2.5. The 750 μm length and 300 μm base diameter provide a balance between penetration depth and mechanical strength. These needles are expected to provide a smoother penetration experience compared to the sharp conical needles of Design 2, reducing discomfort while still maintaining efficient skin penetration. The spacing between needles (800 μm) ensures sufficient room for each needle to perform its function without interference. The overall design is likely to offer a more reliable mechanical performance and may reduce the risk of breaking or bending while ensuring effective drug delivery.

Figure 7: Square Pyramidal Patch (Control)

Design 2: High-Aspect-Ratio Sharp Conical Needles

- **Length:** 800 μm
- **Base Diameter:** 300 μm

- **Aspect Ratio:** 2.67 (sharpest)
- **Needle-to-Needle Spacing:** 800 μm
- **Number of Needles:** 100 (10x10 array)
- **Geometry:** Conical

Design 2 features sharp, high-aspect-ratio conical needles designed to maximize skin penetration. The sharp conical shape is expected to allow for easy and efficient skin insertion, leading to faster drug delivery. With an aspect ratio of 2.67, these needles are the sharpest, which should reduce pain during the initial puncture.

Figure 8: Sharp Conical Microneedle Patch

However, the high aspect ratio also makes these needles more prone to bending or breaking if not optimized for mechanical strength [10]. The smaller base diameter (300 μm) and relatively high length (800 μm) are expected to provide a good balance between sharpness and penetration depth, but careful testing will be necessary to ensure that the needles retain structural integrity under stress while still achieving effective drug release [10].

Design 3: Low-Aspect-Ratio Cylindrical Needles

- **Length:** 700 μm
- **Base Diameter:** 300 μm
- **Aspect Ratio:** 2.33 (blunt)

- **Needle-to-Needle Spacing:** 800 μm
- **Number of Needles:** 100 (10x10 array)
- **Geometry:** Cylindrical

Design 3 features blunt cylindrical needles with a lower aspect ratio of 2.33, designed to prioritize comfort during insertion. These blunt needles are less likely to cause pain during penetration, making them ideal for applications where patient comfort is crucial.

Figure 9: Cylindrical shaped Microneedle Patch

However, this geometry is expected to reduce penetration efficiency compared to sharper designs. The 700 μm length ensures that the needles reach an appropriate depth for drug delivery, while the 300 μm base diameter and the blunt design are meant to offer enhanced mechanical stability, preventing breakage during use. This design may also offer slower, more sustained drug release, as the cylindrical geometry may hold more drug within the needle, allowing for controlled release over time.

Hybrid Designs (Pyramid with Cylindrical Needles)

- **Pyramidal Length:** 750 μm
- **Cylindrical Length:** 700 μm

- **Base Diameter:** 300 μm
- **Aspect Ratio:** Varying from 2.5 to 2.33
- **Needle-to-Needle Spacing:** 800 μm
- **Geometry:** Pyramidal and Cylindrical

These two designs combine both pyramidal and cylindrical geometries to create a hybrid microneedle that could potentially offer the best of both worlds. The pyramidal needles (750 μm long, aspect ratio 2.5) will provide efficient skin penetration, while the cylindrical needles (700 μm long, aspect ratio 2.33) offer more stability and comfort. This hybrid design is expected to balance the sharpness needed for fast drug delivery with the mechanical strength required for a durable microneedle. It will likely produce better results than either design on its own, as the pyramidal needles will penetrate efficiently, while the cylindrical needles will prevent breakage and enhance patient comfort [10][11].

Hybrid Design 1: Alternate Needles

- **Needle Arrangement:** Alternating rows of pyramidal and cylindrical needles
- **Number of Needles:** 100 (10x10 array)

Figure 10: Alternate rows of pyramidal and cylindrical needles

This design alternates pyramidal and cylindrical needles in rows to create a microneedle array that benefits from both sharp penetration and reduced discomfort. The expected effect is a compromise between pain reduction and drug delivery efficiency. The pyramidal needles will pierce the skin more easily, while the cylindrical needles will help to reduce discomfort and provide additional structural support. This alternating pattern may also lead to more uniform drug release, with sharp and blunt needles working together to ensure a smooth and controlled delivery [11].

Hybrid Design 2: Cylindrical Core with Pyramidal Exterior

- **Needle Arrangement:** 6x6 array of cylindrical needles surrounded by pyramidal needles
- **Number of Needles:** 100 (10x10 array)

This hybrid configuration places cylindrical needles at the core of the array, surrounded by pyramidal needles. The central cylindrical needles provide a stable, comfortable core, while the outer pyramidal needles offer sharper penetration. This design is expected to combine effective drug delivery with minimal discomfort. The pyramidal exterior should allow for quicker penetration, while the cylindrical core might ensure that the drug is delivered slowly and more evenly over time, resulting in a balanced overall performance. [12]

Figure 11: Core of cylindrical needles surrounded by pyramidal needles

3.2.3 3D Printing Process and Specifications

To create these designs, SLA (Stereolithography) 3D printing was used. SLA was chosen because it provides high resolution, making it suitable for printing small, intricate structures like microneedles. The printer used for this project had a resolution of 15 microns, ensuring that the designs were accurately reproduced. Multiple designs were printed together in one batch to save time and ensure consistency across samples. The resulting master molds, with their fine details, will be used for micro-molding the actual microneedles. These prototypes will then be tested for their performance, drug release, and overall usability.

MATERIAL SYNTHESIS

4.1 Material Selection and Rationale

Biocompatibility, biodegradability, and mechanical performance were critical factors guiding material selection. A hybrid matrix was developed using sodium alginate and gelatin, both of which are FDA-approved for biomedical use. To enhance hydration, skin adhesion, and biocompatibility, hyaluronic acid (HA) was incorporated as the backing layer. Freeze-drying was chosen to preserve the structural and functional integrity of the microneedles and ensure high drug stability. Additionally, lysozyme is used as a model drug instead as it shares several physicochemical characteristics with insulin, such as molecular weight range, hydrophilicity, and a similar absorption peak at 280 nm. This is further detailed in chapter 6 [13].

4.2 Sodium Alginate-Gelatin Blend cross-linked with Calcium Chloride

The matrix in which insulin was loaded was made up of sodium alginate and gelatin to offer us better properties of sodium alginate. This chemical, though, offers amazing properties like biodegradability, biocompatibility, and film-forming capability among others. The microneedles made up of just sodium alginate exhibit poor mechanical strength. Therefore, to improve their mechanical strength we use calcium ions from calcium chloride to form cross-linked alginate microneedles. When these are mixed with a polysaccharide like gelatin which provides better strength due to a large number of hydroxyl groups in these polysaccharides [13][14].

4.2.1 Material and Apparatus

The following materials and equipment were used to create the hydrogel matrix for the microneedles

- Sodium Alginate and Gelatin powder
- Calcium Chloride
- Lysozyme Powder
- Deionized water
- Measuring cylinders
- 100 ml beakers
- Petri dish
- Weighing balance
- Heating oven
- Magnetic stirrer and hot plate
- Centrifuge
- Aluminum foil

4.2.2 Procedure for Microneedle Matrix

The procedure recorded below was used to create the needle matrix containing the loaded drug [13].

1. 0.5g of sodium alginate was dissolved in 10 mL of deionized water at room temperature with stirring.
2. This mixture was then placed on the hot plate and agitated using a magnetic stirrer for 1.5 hours at 50°C.
3. After ensuring the complete dissolution of sodium alginate and the formation of a homogenous mixture, 0.4g of gelatin powder was added to the mixture and stirred on the hot plate at 50°C for 4 hours.
4. Degas the mixture using a centrifuge at 3500 rpm for 15 minutes to remove air bubbles.

5. Dissolve 10 mg/mL of lysozyme in a separate container with a minimal volume of deionized water (1–2 mL).

6. Stir the dissolved powder in the deionized water and add this solution to the 10 mL gelatin-sodium alginate solution. Keep mixing to ensure that drug is uniformly distributed in the blend.

7. Moreover, a 2% solution of calcium chloride was prepared by adding 0.1g calcium chloride (CaCl_2) in 5 mL of deionized water and mixed thoroughly. This solution will serve the crosslinking function later.

4.2.2 Procedure for Hyaluronic Acid Backing Plate

The materials used were [13]:

- Hyaluronic Acid
- Deionized water
- 100 mL Beakers and weighing balance
- Magnetic stirrer and hot plate

The following procedure was used to make the backing layer:

1. Weigh 0.5 g of 6 kDa HA using a precision weighing balance.
2. Gradually add the HA powder to 10 mL of deionized water in a beaker.
3. Place the beaker on a magnetic stirrer with a hot plate.
4. Stir the mixture at room temperature or slightly warm (30–40°C) for 2–3 hours to ensure complete dissolution.

4.3 Micro-molding Fabrication Technique

After preparing the polymer solutions, the next objective is to prepare negative molds of the microneedles through micro-molding fabrication, as detailed [7]:

1. A 10:1 ratio of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) base and curing agent (Sylgard 184) was prepared in a clean beaker.
2. The mixture was stirred thoroughly for 5–10 minutes to ensure homogeneous blending of the components.
3. To eliminate entrapped air bubbles, the PDMS degassed for approximately 20–30 minutes until all visible bubbles were removed.
4. Meanwhile, 3D-printed microneedle arrays (used as master molds) were affixed to the base of a Petri dish using double-sided adhesive tape, with the needles oriented facing upward.
5. The degassed PDMS mixture was carefully poured over the master mold, fully submerging the microneedles while ensuring minimal disturbance to their positioning.
6. The setup was allowed to cure at room temperature for 24 hours or alternatively cured at 60°C for 2–3 hours to accelerate the process.
7. Once cured, the solidified PDMS layer was gently peeled off, producing a negative mold that contained precise inverse features of the microneedle geometry.

Figure 12: Negative PDMS mold peeled from a 3d printed master mold

4.4 Freeze Drying

Freeze drying is a crucial part of the fabrication process. After preparing the polymer solutions, these are poured into the replica molds, are subsequently placed in a lyophilizer. The lyophilizer simultaneously sublimates and dries the material to remove all moisture, which directly contributes to mechanical strength, increased drug diffusion, and improved shelf life [7].

Figure 13: Detailed methodology for the synthesis of microneedle patches through micro-molding fabrication and freeze-drying

The following steps were taken [15]:

1. After preparing the drug-loaded sodium alginate–gelatin polymer solution, 200 μL of solution is pipetted into the negative PDMS molds, ensuring complete cavity filling. Each patch thus, is loaded with 200 μg of lysozyme.
2. The filled molds were placed into a freezer at -5°C to -10°C for several hours (typically 4–6 hours) to initiate solidification of the polymer matrix [15].
3. Once adequately frozen, calcium chloride (CaCl_2) solution was poured onto the surface of the frozen patches to initiate ionic crosslinking with the alginate.

4. The molds were left undisturbed for 2–3 hours at room temperature to allow for sufficient crosslinking between Ca^{2+} ions and alginate chains.
5. After crosslinking, the prepared hyaluronic acid solution was pipetted onto the surface of the semi-solid matrix to form a backing layer.
6. The entire setup was again vacuumized briefly to remove trapped air and to allow the backing layer to integrate properly with the underlying matrix.
7. Finally, the molds were placed in a freeze-dryer (lyophilizer) and processed at -40°C and 0.05 mbar pressure for a total of 6 hours, resulting in structurally stable, porous microneedle patches suitable for transdermal application [15].

CHARACTERIZATION AND TESTING

5.1 X-ray Diffraction Analysis

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed to evaluate the crystalline or amorphous nature of the microneedle patch components and to study the effect of drying methods on crystallinity.

While crystalline structures generally offer higher stiffness, amorphous structures such as those in freeze-dried hydrogels provide greater flexibility, higher swelling, and better drug diffusion due to the lack of long-range order and greater “free volume” or empty space between molecules, provides more pathways and larger gaps for drug molecules to move through, making them favorable for controlled drug release in transdermal applications [16].

Figure 14: XRD spectrum of the freeze-dried gelatin-SA matrix

The XRD pattern above reveals that the freeze-dried gelatin-SA blend exhibited broader, less defined peaks, indicative of a highly amorphous structure. This can be attributed to rapid freezing and sublimation of water during lyophilization, which prevents polymer chains from organizing into crystalline domains.

In contrast, air-dried samples generally display sharper, more intense peaks, suggesting a relatively higher degree of crystallinity due to slower solvent evaporation and enhanced molecular packing.

The XRD results therefore support the intended functional properties of the microneedle patch.

5.2 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR spectroscopy was conducted to confirm the presence of key functional groups and to detect any changes in chemical bonding due to formulation or drying [16].

Figure 15: FTIR spectra for air-dried and freeze-dried blends

Both air-dried and freeze-dried samples showed characteristic absorption bands. 3200–3500 cm^{-1} region shows broad peaks corresponding to O–H and N–H stretching, indicating hydrogen bonding and moisture content. Freeze-dried samples exhibited broader bands, consistent with higher retained water and more hydrogen bonding. 1600–1650 cm^{-1} shows the amide I band from C=O stretching in gelatin. Amide II band due to N–H bending and C–N stretching can be seen in the 1500–1550 cm^{-1} region. Symmetric stretching of COO^- indicate the presence of alginate. C–O–C stretching indicative of the polysaccharide backbone. Moreover, the hydrogen bonding and moisture retention observed in the freeze-dried samples suggest enhanced crosslinking and network stability, which positively impacts swelling and drug release behavior.

5.3 Optical Microscopy

To visually assess the morphology and replication precision of the microneedle structures, optical microscopy was conducted on the final microneedle patches. The top-view images showed both circular and square-based microneedles arranged in a uniform array [16].

Figure 16: Image showing microneedle patch with a circular base (cylindrical and conical needles)

Figure 17: Image showing a patch with a square base (square pyramidal needles)

Figure 18: Square based needles without dimension lines

Base diameter of the microneedles was set at 300 μm , as seen on the scale bar. The diameters of the needle bases appear quite close to 300 μm . This uniformity confirms that the PDMS mold accurately replicated the 3D-printed master mold, and that the polymer solution (gelatin–alginate) properly filled the cavities during casting. No evidence of collapsed, incomplete, or irregularly shaped microneedles was observed, suggesting effective fabrication and drying processes.

The sharpness and defined edges of the microneedles are critical for minimizing insertion force and enhancing skin penetration efficiency.

5.4 Mechanical Strength Testing

Compression testing is a critical evaluation method to assess whether the microneedles can withstand the axial forces encountered during skin insertion without bending or breaking. In this study, a force vs. displacement curve was obtained using a universal testing machine.

The curve revealed that the maximum force endured by the pyramidal patch was 2.583 N, occurring at a displacement of 0.312 mm. Given that the patch contained 100 microneedles, the calculated force per needle is approximately 0.026 N.

In comparison, literature indicates that a minimum of 0.028–0.030 N per needle is typically required to penetrate the human stratum corneum effectively [16]. Although

the measured force per needle is slightly below this threshold, it is within proximity, indicating promising mechanical stability and the potential for successful insertion with slight modifications.

Figure 19: Compression force vs displacement curve for the control patch

The fluctuations in the force curve are common in microneedle systems, especially those made from natural biopolymers. These irregularities can be attributed to micro-buckling, crack initiation, or variability in polymer density caused by freeze-drying. However, the overall upward trend and integrity of the structure up to the peak force confirm that microneedles possess adequate strength for potential skin penetration [17].

5.5 Swelling Ratio

The swelling behavior of the microneedle patch was studied in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at 37 °C to simulate skin conditions. During insertion, interstitial fluid of the skin permeates the patch due to capillary action, causing the patch to swell up

[18]. The swelling ratio directly dictates the amount of drug release. Greater the swelling, greater the drug release. Therefore, a swelling test was conducted to determine the swelling ratio of the patch.

Figure 20: Swelling ratio of the freeze-dried SA-gelatin blend

The swelling curve indicated that the patch absorbed fluid rapidly during the first 60 minutes, reaching a swelling ratio of over 300%, and gradually approached equilibrium at approximately 410% swelling after 210 minutes.

This high swelling capacity is characteristic of hydrophilic biopolymers like gelatin and alginate and indicates effective fluid uptake and retention within the polymer network [19]. The porous structure formed during freeze-drying facilitates rapid water entry, while hydrogen bonding between polymer chains maintains network integrity and prevents dissolution [20].

DRUG RELEASE TESTING

6.1 Introduction

6.1.1 Purpose of Drug Release Testing for Microneedle Patches

Drug release testing is a vital component in the evaluation of microneedle-based transdermal systems. It helps determine how efficiently the loaded therapeutic agent is released into the body over time once the patch is applied to the skin. This *in vitro* testing simulates physiological conditions and allows for assessment of formulation effectiveness, polymer matrix behavior, and the influence of microneedle geometry on drug diffusion. The release profile informs design choices, particularly for controlled or sustained drug delivery applications.

6.1.2 Rationale for Lysozyme as a Model Drug for Insulin

Due to the high cost and handling sensitivity of insulin, lysozyme was selected as a model protein drug for this study. Lysozyme shares several physicochemical characteristics with insulin, such as molecular weight range, hydrophilicity, and most importantly, a similar absorption peak at 280 nm, which allows for straightforward quantification via UV-Vis spectroscopy. The use of lysozyme allows for economical and practical simulation of insulin release behavior during preliminary stages of development [21].

6.2 Materials and Apparatus

The following materials and equipment were used to prepare standard drug solutions for the calibration curve.

1. Lysozyme Powder
2. PBS pellets
3. De-ionized water
4. Beakers

5. Magnetic Stirrers
6. Pipette
7. Weighing Balance
8. Volumetric Flasks
9. Mortar and Pestle
10. Aluminum Foil
11. Hotplate

6.2.1 Procedure for Lysozyme Calibration Curve:

The following procedure was used for making standard solutions of lysozyme powder to create the calibration curve [21]:

1. Accurately weigh out lysozyme powder and dissolve it in Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS) solution to create a concentrated stock solution (e.g., 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Ensure complete dissolution.
2. From the stock solution, prepare a series of diluted standard solutions in PBS at the following concentrations: 100, 300, 500, 700, and 900 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.
3. Using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer, blank the instrument with PBS at 280 nm. Subsequently, measure and record the absorbance of each prepared standard solution at 280 nm.
4. Plot the measured absorbance values (y-axis) against their corresponding lysozyme concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) (x-axis). Perform linear regression analysis to obtain the calibration curve equation ($y = mx + c$) and the coefficient of determination (R^2).

6.2.2 Calibration Curve

The prepared standard concentrations of 100, 300, 500, 700 and 900 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ were placed in the UV-Vis spectrophotometer and their absorbance was measured at 280 nm (which is the detection wavelength of both insulin and lysozyme). The recorded

absorbance values ranged from 0.2491 to 1.6974 with an R^2 value of 0.9961, demonstrating a strong linear relationship between concentration and absorbance.

Figure 21: Calibration curve of the lysozyme drug

A linear regression was performed to fit the calibration curve, yielding an equation of the form:

$$\mathbf{Absorbance = 1.8777 * (Concentration) + 0.0459}$$
$$\mathbf{R^2 = 0.9964}$$

This equation was used to calculate the lysozyme concentration in unknown samples during drug release testing by plugging in their absorbance values. This method allowed accurate and reliable quantification of lysozyme, a model drug, throughout the release study.

6.3 Determination of Concentration from Absorbance

The drug release behavior of microneedle patches was evaluated using lysozyme as a model protein, and UV-Vis spectroscopy at 280 nm for quantification. Five distinct patch morphologies were tested:

1. Square Pyramidal (Control)
2. Conical
3. Cylindrical
4. Square Pyramid
5. Hybrid Designs
 - a. Alternating Needle Geometry
 - b. Core + Exterior Needle Variation

Each microneedle patch was initially loaded with 200 µg/mL of lysozyme. The patches were then immersed in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at 37 °C, and samples were taken at predefined time intervals (0–180 minutes). The absorbance of each sample was measured at 280 nm using UV-Vis spectrophotometry.

Using the linear equation obtained from the lysozyme calibration curve, unknown lysozyme concentrations were calculated from known absorbances through the relation:

$$\text{Concentration} = \frac{\text{Absorbance} - 0.0459}{1.8777}$$

These concentrations were then used to determine the cumulative drug release percentage over time for each patch morphology. The detailed tabulated results for each patch morphology are presented below:

Table 1: In vitro drug release data for square-pyramidal patch

Time (min)	Absorbance	Concentration (mg/mL)	Cumulative Concentration (mg/mL)	% Release
0	0.0459	0	0	0
30	0.0636	0.0094	0.0094	4.7
60	0.0851	0.0209	0.0303	15.15
90	0.1103	0.0348	0.0651	32.55
120	0.1271	0.0437	0.1088	54.4
180	0.1353	0.0476	0.1564	78.2

Table 2: In vitro drug release data for conical patch

Time (min)	Absorbance	Concentration (mg/mL)	Cumulative Concentration (mg/mL)	% Release
0	0.0459	0	0	0
30	0.0665	0.011	0.011	5.5
60	0.0897	0.0228	0.0338	16.9
90	0.1134	0.036	0.0698	34.9
120	0.1299	0.0448	0.1146	57.3
180	0.1378	0.0485	0.1631	81.55

Table 3: In vitro drug release data for cylindrical patch

Time (min)	Absorbance	Concentration (mg/mL)	Cumulative Concentration (mg/mL)	% Release
0	0.0459	0	0	0
30	0.0577	0.0063	0.0063	3.15

60	0.073	0.015	0.0213	10.65
90	0.1003	0.029	0.0503	25.15
120	0.1178	0.0383	0.0886	44.3
180	0.1263	0.043	0.1316	65.8

Table 4: In vitro drug release data for hybrid patch with alternating rows

Time (min)	Absorbance	Concentration (mg/mL)	Cumulative Concentration (mg/mL)	% Release
0	0.0459	0	0	0
30	0.0605	0.0078	0.0078	3.9
60	0.0795	0.0179	0.0257	12.85
90	0.1058	0.0319	0.0576	28.8
120	0.1227	0.0409	0.0985	49.25
180	0.1301	0.0453	0.1438	71.9

Table 5: In vitro drug release data for hybrid patch with cylindrical core and pyramidal exterior

Time (min)	Absorbance	Concentration (mg/mL)	Cumulative Concentration (mg/mL)	% Release
0	0.0459	0	0	0
30	0.0617	0.0084	0.0084	4.2
60	0.0812	0.0193	0.0277	13.85
90	0.108	0.0331	0.0608	30.4
120	0.124	0.0421	0.1029	51.45
180	0.1313	0.046	0.1489	74.45

The cumulative drug release percentage was simply calculated using the formula:

$$\%age\ Drug\ Release = \frac{Cumulative\ Drug\ Concentration}{Drug\ Loaded\ In\ Each\ Patch\ (200\mu g)} * 100\%$$

6.4 Drug Release Profiles

The cumulative drug release profiles from all five microneedle geometries were obtained from the tables above to construct the following drug release vs time graph:

Figure 22: Drug release profiles from all 5 distinct patches

The cumulative drug release curves demonstrate clear differences in release behavior based on needle shape, geometry, and likely differences in crosslinking density, surface area, and diffusion path length [22].

1. Conical (Highest Release ~82%)

The conical design exhibited the highest cumulative release of lysozyme over the 3-hour period. This can be attributed to several factors:

- Sharp tip and narrow shaft geometry offer a large surface-area-to-volume ratio, promoting rapid fluid uptake and dissolution.
- Conical structures also minimize drug entrapment in thick regions of the polymer, enhancing diffusion.
- The sharp geometry allows for more efficient swelling of the biopolymer network and faster lysozyme escape into the surrounding PBS.

2. Square Pyramidal (Control, ~78%)

The control group also showed high release, slightly lower than the conical type. Square pyramids:

- Provide moderate surface exposure, balancing between mechanical strength and diffusivity.
- Likely form a uniform crosslinked matrix with CaCl_2 due to even shape and polymer distribution, allowing for consistent swelling and release.
- The planar faces may slow diffusion slightly compared to conical tips due to broader base regions.

3. Hybrid Microneedles

The hybrid geometries (e.g., **alternating rows** and **core–exterior variation**) showed **intermediate release behavior**:

- In hybrid A, alternating sharp and blunt needles likely create heterogeneous swelling zones. This leads to slightly staggered diffusion rates, which may explain the moderate release (~72%).
- Hybrid B, where core and peripheral needles differ in design, could exhibit non-uniform drug distribution or variable polymer thickness, causing the core needles to release slower due to reduced exposure to PBS (~74.4).

- These hybrid designs, while innovative for controlling mechanical and insertion behavior, introduce diffusion path variability that slightly slowed total release.

4. Cylindrical (Lowest Release ~66%)

Cylindrical needles consistently showed the lowest cumulative drug release across all time points. Several factors likely contribute:

- Thicker structure and blunt geometry reduce the exposed surface area for dissolution.
- Cylinders tend to swell more slowly and may retain moisture internally, delaying drug outward diffusion.
- Additionally, their bulkier polymer body means that lysozyme embedded deeper within the needle faces a longer path to escape, especially if the CaCl_2 crosslinking is denser in thicker sections.
- These designs may also retain more crosslinking agent, forming a denser hydrogel matrix and thus slowing lysozyme diffusion.

6.4.1 Influence of CaCl_2 Crosslinking

All microneedle patches were crosslinked using CaCl_2 , which reacts with sodium alginate to form an ionically crosslinked hydrogel network. The extent and distribution of crosslinking affects:

- Swelling behavior as higher crosslink density reduces swelling and therefore slows drug release.
- Network porosity as lower crosslinking leads to a looser network with larger pores, facilitating faster diffusion.

The release differences observed may be partly due to how Ca^{2+} ions penetrate differently into needle geometries. In slender designs (e.g., conical), Ca^{2+} penetrates uniformly, producing a less dense matrix, aiding drug diffusion. Whereas, in thicker

geometries (e.g., cylindrical), localized dense crosslinking likely occurs, impeding release [23].

6.4.2 Implications of Lysozyme Release for Insulin Delivery

Lysozyme was used in this study as a model drug for insulin due to their similar molecular weights, hydrophilicity, and UV absorbance behavior (280 nm). The successful release of lysozyme from various microneedle geometries suggests that insulin would exhibit comparable diffusion kinetics, assuming similar loading and environmental conditions [21].

The observed release durations of 3 hours or more are particularly promising for insulin, which requires sustained delivery to maintain basal blood glucose levels. Fast-releasing geometries (tapered pyramid, conical) could mimic bolus insulin delivery, while slower designs (cylindrical, hybrid) may support basal delivery profiles. This provides a basis for tailoring needle morphology to suit patient-specific insulin dosing strategies.

Furthermore, the results validate the use of biopolymer-based microneedles for delivering sensitive protein therapeutics, provided that hydration and matrix degradation can be carefully controlled.

6.4.3 Limitations and Future Considerations

While the drug release profiles provide valuable insights, several limitations should be acknowledged:

1. Model Drug Limitation:

Lysozyme, although structurally and spectrally similar to insulin, is not a perfect analog. Insulin has a different tertiary structure and may interact differently with the polymer matrix [21].

2. In Vitro Conditions:

PBS immersion does not fully replicate the complex biochemical environment of human skin, including enzyme activity, interstitial fluid dynamics, or immune response.

3. Patch Uniformity:

Slight variations in microneedle height, base diameter, and drug loading may influence release profiles, especially in hybrid designs.

4. No Release Kinetics Modeling:

Mathematical models were not applied in this study but could help predict real-world performance and optimize future formulations.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Conclusion

Our project demonstrated the design, fabrication, and evaluation of biodegradable microneedle patches for transdermal delivery of insulin using the model drug lysozyme. Using a combination of gelatin, sodium alginate, and hyaluronic acid, five distinct microneedle geometries were developed and fabricated via 3D printing and PDMS molding, followed by freeze-drying.

Comprehensive characterization confirmed the mechanical strength, chemical integrity, and swelling behavior of the patches. The patches exhibited a maximum compressive force of 2.583 N, translating to a per-needle force of ~ 0.026 N, which is close to the literature-reported minimum for skin penetration.

In vitro drug release testing using lysozyme as a model protein confirmed the influence of microneedle geometry on release kinetics. Conical and square pyramidal designs demonstrated superior release performance, while cylindrical geometries exhibited slower, more sustained profiles. These results indicate that needle shape, surface area, and crosslinking density play critical roles in determining the release behavior of transdermal systems.

Future Prospects

Building upon the findings of this study, several future directions can enhance the development and translational potential of microneedle-based drug delivery systems:

1. In vivo testing using animal models to assess actual skin penetration depth, pharmacokinetics, and insulin bioavailability.
2. Incorporation of real insulin into the microneedle matrix to study protein stability, activity, and therapeutic efficacy post-administration.
3. Kinetic modeling of drug release data to better understand diffusion mechanisms and predict long-term performance.

4. Commercial scaling and regulatory evaluation for future clinical trials and real-world deployment.

With continued research and optimization, microneedle patches such as those developed in this study hold strong potential to revolutionize transdermal delivery, especially for chronic conditions like diabetes requiring frequent, controlled drug administration.

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